

ECONOMY

REGARDING THE HUMANITARIAN AND ECONOMIC LOSSES CAUSED BY THE RUSSIAN-UKRAINIAN WAR: FEATURES OF OVERCOMING THE HUMANITARIAN CRISIS

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Abstract

The article analyzes the humanitarian and economic losses caused by the Russian-Ukrainian war in Ukraine. The impact of a full-scale invasion on the country's economy, in particular agriculture, ecology and culture, has been assessed. A methodology for assessing war damage based on the analysis of historical data related to more than 150 wars in the world since 1870 has been considered. Depending on their duration and intensity, there may be different consequences for the economy of countries. The "carried forward effect" calculated by them, which will be affected by other countries, takes into account, first of all, trade ties that exist due to geographical proximity, and the size of the national economy of the country in which the war is going on.

The article provides detailed data on infrastructure losses in the humanitarian sphere, especially among cultural facilities. Separately, the role of the Moscow church in conducting a hybrid war on the territory of Ukraine and spreading the ideas of the "Russian world" is highlighted, contributing to its development into a large-scale Russian invasion of Ukraine in 2022, is highlighted.

Keywords: Ukrainian State, adept, Russian-Ukrainian war, hybrid war, full-scale military invasion, temporarily occupied territory, economic recovery, war losses.

Relevance of the study. The date of February 24, 2022 will be deeply wounded in the historical memory of not only the Ukrainian people, but also the whole modern world. The recent history of Ukraine is marked with the most tragic and dramatic events – a full-scale military invasion of the Russian Federation preceded for a long time by a long hybrid war, using all possible conventional and non-conventional tools of influence. Russia's barbaric, aggressive, unprovoked invasion of Ukraine is not only a manifestation of a huge security threat that has destroyed peaceful life in Europe, but also has triggered global changes in the world life. This war is based on the Rushism ideology of the "Russian world", which is the basic narrative of the state policy of the Russian Federation.

Therefore, to address the issue of damage caused to the Russian-Ukrainian economy and social sector of Ukraine, which is at the heart of the features of the humanitarian crisis, the study of this topic is quite **relevant** and practical-oriented.

The goal of the study is to analyze the humanitarian and economic damage caused by the Russian-Ukrainian war to Ukraine and the specifics of regulating and resolving the humanitarian crisis caused by this war.

Scholars of various scientific fields, mainly economists, political scientists, sociologists, lawyers and specialists in the science of public administration, pay attention to the study of this topic. It is worth highlighting the works of A. Becker [3], A. Dubrovenko [6], Ya. Zhalilo [7], V. Zaluzhnyi [8], A. Komarchuk [9], Liz

Olderman [10], R. Shpel [16], Kyiv School of Economics (KSE) [11], representatives of BDO as an international network of public accounting, tax and advisory firms [12], working out methods for assessing losses from the Russian-Ukrainian war both for Ukraine and for the entire world economy.

Their essence is to determine the damage, amount of losses and lost profits in connection with the armed aggression of the Russian Federation in accordance with the Order "On Approval of the Methodology for Determining the Damage and Amount of Losses Caused to Enterprises, Institutions and Organizations of All Forms of Ownership As a Result of Destruction and Damage to Their Property in Connection with the Armed Aggression of the Russian Federation, As Well As Lost Profits From the Impossibility or Obstacles in the Implementation of Economic Activities", approved on October 18, 2022 jointly with the Ministry of Economy of Ukraine and the State Property Fund of Ukraine [13].

Description of the problem. The large-scale invasion of the Russian Federation was preceded by an information and hybrid war, which was supposed to prepare the socio-political ground for the direct armed annexation of the territory and the treacherous invasion of the Russian occupier in Ukraine, which actually began on February 20, 2014. We consider the essence of hybrid warfare as "a set of pre-prepared and promptly implemented actions of a military, diplomatic and informational nature aimed at achieving strategic goals. It includes the implementation of a complex of hybrid

threats of various types, namely: traditional and non-standard, large-scale terrorism, as well as subversive actions, during which innovative technology is used to counter the enemy's military force, such as massive cyber attacks, subversive actions in the energy and economic spheres, etc." [9]. It is no coincidence that on the eve of the full-scale invasion of the Russian Federation, virtually all military depots have been destroyed in Ukraine, and political forces – collaborators and the main pillar of the "Russian world" in Ukraine – the Ukrainian Orthodox Church of the Moscow Patriarchate – have gained considerable activity in the public sector.

The activities of adherents of the "Russian world" in Ukraine, as well as collaborators of the aggressor country, are part of a plan of the Russian Federation to eliminate Ukrainian statehood, which should help Russian fascism. But the aggressor did not take into account the level of maturity of civil society in Ukraine, which really turned out to be stronger than state structures, showed a dominant rejection and hatred of its representatives, and rallied in defense of Ukrainian statehood [17].

Regarding the concept and ideology of the "Russian world", it is worth noting that this is "the Russian neo-imperial rushist geopolitical and ideological doctrine of the era of Putinism rule, the orientation of the Russian population regarding the ideological foundations of the existence and development of Russian society through the formation of a symbiosis of the historical past and a promising vision of the future in the search for a new model of ideological filling of the national idea of the new Russian Empire. It provides for the creation of a strategy of geopolitical development on the territory of the former Soviet Union, mass- and socio-communication technology of the influence of the Russian Federation on the internal policy of neighboring states, socio-political practice and eclectic worldview mixture in party construction and ideological and propaganda activities, an ideological concept in the political and intellectual discourse of the Russian Federation to denote supranational and transcontinental community. It is a complex political technology of the Kremlin and a geopolitical approach for interpreting modern political processes of the right and left spectra in one channel in the form of eclectic combinations of elements of pan-Slavism, Eurasianism, Russian Messianism and imperialism (including in the form of an informal empire), the ideology of Russian Bolshevism and the extreme nationalist movements of the Russian white anti-communist movement during the years of the Russian civil war in exile [17].

"Russian world" is a narrative aimed at restoring Russian imperial dominance in the post-socialist space. This is a concept created by a state in a state of decline, which dreams of its former greatness.

The Moscow church in Ukraine is an aggressive adept of the "Russian world". An adept (from Latin "*adeptus*" means who has achieved) is a zealous supporter of any teaching, idea [A]. The "Russian world" is also defined as a common "civilizational space", which is based on the three principles: orthodoxy, Russian culture and especially the Russian language, a

poorly camouflaged autocracy (dictatorship), presented as "a common historical memory and common views on social development". In Russia, this is how they began to idealize the former autocracy mixed with Stalinism. Moreover, one of the leading adherents of the "Russian world", patriarch Kirill of the Russian Orthodox Church (FSB officer Gundiaev), has noted the same thing that the foundations of the "Russian world" are: Orthodox faith, Russian language and culture, common historical memory and common views on social development. This triune formula of foundations – "pillars" is the latest reissue (modification) of the earlier state formula of the 19th century in the Russian Empire, which the dictator Putin wants to put as the basis of the newest Empire. Therefore, the Moscow church in Ukraine, having almost military subordination, just performs the role of an adept of the "Russian world" and is a kind of watchman of these three pillars in Ukraine.

According to the General V. Zaluzhnyi, in the situation that has developed with the defense of our state, there are still "a number of factors that certainly affect the decision to search for new forms of using the defense forces. Here are some of them: the unstable political situation around Ukraine, which leads to a reduction in military support; the high probability of Russia provoking a number of more conflicts (Israel and Yemen) and distracting the main partners from supporting Ukraine" [8] and the aggressor's use of sophisticated and latest forms of information warfare, especially in social networks that are mostly Russian-speaking and nostalgic for the USSR, to create such political instability. Using sophisticated tools for conducting information warfare, the Russian Federation, especially due to the influence of religion on the individual, turns it into a moral Zombie, which is sometimes capable of anything for proximity to the "servant of God".

One of the most sophisticated mechanisms of such influence is the Internet and social communications, which continue to largely adhere to the ideas of the Russian World. As a rule, the *Moscow church* has in its ranks representatives of law enforcement agencies disguised as clergy. Quite often, the political influence of the media, which consists in their ability to meet the communicative needs of the population, is made through it. The more valuable the information is provided to the mass media, the more important the media becomes, its political positions are strengthened, and the dependence of "consumers" on it deepens. This position is derived from the theoretical concept of "satisfaction of needs", which states that different models of perception and use of media are formed in accordance with the communicative needs of the population and how it evaluates the ability of mass media to meet their needs" [5]. Realizing this, the Moscow church, acting as an adept of the "Russian world" in Ukraine, actively uses information resources, especially the Internet (mostly Russian-speaking) for aggressive and soft dissemination of the ideas of the "Russian world". The soft spread of its ideas occurs as the spread of interesting nostalgic Soviet themes, usually via the Internet.

Although a significant part of Ukrainian society understands this problem, unfortunately, the state still

does not act decisively enough to protect its interests. On the eve of the full-scale invasion of the Russian Federation in Ukraine, amendments to the Law “On Freedom of Conscience and Religious Organizations” [On Separate] came into force. According to the new rules, churches and religious institutions had to change their names in the Unified State Register so that it was clear that the organization belonged to the Moscow Patriarchate. Otherwise, such amendments were made forcibly. On December 01, 2022, the President of Ukraine V. Zelenskyi put into effect the decision of the National Security and Defense Council on “Banning the Activities of Religious Organizations Affiliated with Centers of Influence in Russia in Ukraine” [15]. We are waiting for the final approval of the Law.

But now, 8,193 churches of the Ukrainian Orthodox Church (Moscow Patriarchate) continue to operate in Ukraine. 99% or 8119 of them, despite the requirements of the Law, have not yet shown belonging to the Patriarchate of the aggressor country in their name. The largest number of churches associated with the aggressor country is recorded in Donetsk region – 683. A significant number of religious institutions of this church has also remained in Vinnytsia Region – 534. Dnipropetrovsk Region (527) and Khmelnytskyi Region (506) are included in the anti-rating. During the active phase of the Russian-Ukrainian war, 589 Ukrainian religious communities moved from the Ukrainian Orthodox Church under the Moscow Patriarchate of the aggressor country to the Ukrainian Orthodox Church. Most religious institutions changed their jurisdiction in Kyiv Region (138), Khmelnytskyi Region (125) and Vinnytsia Region (67) [4]. Being the main adept of the Russian world in Ukraine, this church tries as carefully as possible to preserve the myth of the cradle of 3 fraternal peoples and the foundations of the Russian Empire: faith with the Church Slavonic language, the Russian language and the falsified imperial history of the “third Rome”.

More structurally, the Russo-Ukrainian war has broken down the entire security architecture patiently built on the continent for decades, including international commitments agreed over the past 30 years. As a senior British general has recently pointed out, it is dangerous to assume that the war against Ukraine is a limited conflict [16].

But not only security on the continent is in the focus of the consequences of a military invasion, the rapid decline of the economy, as one of the results of the war, is not only of a general Ukrainian nature, but also of a general global one. According to the Kyiv School of Economics, the total amount of damage suffered by the country's infrastructure as of January 2024 due to the Russian full-scale invasion has already reached \$155 billion. All spheres of the country's life have suffered losses: staggering losses from destruction in housing stock, damage and destruction of infrastructure, forests, educational and energy sectors, agro-industrial complex and land resources of Ukraine, transport sector, healthcare infrastructure, manufacturing industry.

The main export sectors of Ukraine, being the main part of the country's income before the war, have suffered the greatest damage. The war caused a 35%

drop in exports of everything from wheat to steel in 2022. Agriculture, which was the mainstay of the Ukrainian economy and made it a well-known breadbasket of the world, suffered particularly serious losses [10]. Production processes and supply chains have been interrupted, enterprises and logistics centers are being destroyed, and the worst thing is that human lives are under constant threat. According to the results of a survey conducted by the European Business Association, losses from the war of every 5th entrepreneur amount to more than \$100 thousand. To compensate for losses, first of all, it is essential to record and evaluate them [12].

But the scale of losses continues to grow steadily. The war launched by Russia, especially in Donetsk and Luhansk Regions, and the temporary occupation of Crimea have brought hybrid aggression to a qualitatively different level and revealed new threats to Ukraine's economic sovereignty. In particular, these are: fragmentation of the economic and customs space of the state; expropriation of state property, property of individuals and legal entities in uncontrolled territories, property losses as a result of military operations and terrorist acts; obstruction of military operations and terrorist acts; obstacles to sustainable economic development; physical barriers to the implementation of financial and economic activities in the domestic and foreign markets; disruption of critical infrastructure through physical, economic and informational influence; social discontent in the controlled part of Ukraine; the use of economic dependence to obtain political economic influence to obtain political control, etc. [7].

In the case of the attack on Ukraine, Ukraine's close economic ties with the aggressor country, on the contrary, have become one of the main factors in promoting the aggressor's political narratives. Nevertheless, the war enabled to highlight the strengths of our country's economy, which was able to show a high level of its accommodation and adaptability. In particular, the recovery of GDP by GDP at purchasing power parity was achieved in less than 5 years (according to the World Bank's calculations, in 2018 it amounted to \$534 billion against \$505.4 billion in 2013) [11].

Research methodology. The economic and social losses suffered by Ukraine due to hybrid and open military aggression have been the subject of many domestic and foreign expert studies. Thus, using different methodological approaches, in particular by comparing with possible hypothetical development, if the events of 2014 did not take place, by comparing theoretical and actual indicators, and accordingly such estimates have significant differences in different studies, more often regarding the study of the occupation of certain parts of Donetsk and Luhansk Regions.

The calculation of losses caused to Ukraine by the occupation of Crimea is carried out mainly by a straightforward method and according to the data officially announced by the Ministry of Justice of Ukraine in 2014 amounted to UAH 950 billion (\$84 billion) at the then exchange rate). It is worth focusing on the methodology and basis on which the calculation has been made. The study is based on an analysis of historical data related to more than 150 wars in the world

since 1870. Researchers from the University of Kiel came to various conclusions from this. For example, as for how much, on average, if the war lasts about 5 years, national GDP falls and inflation increases [3].

This “calculation” is based on spending as a result of “typical” interstate wars in the past. Depending on their duration and intensity, more or less severe scenarios are possible” (Jonathan Federle) [3], experts from IfW note. They calculated “the carried forward effect that other countries will feel takes into account, first of all, trade ties that exist due to geographical proximity, and the size of the national economy of the country in which the war is going on”, explains the expert and author of the study, Jonathan Federle [3].

Main content. In 2021, the Center for Economic Strategy published a more complete assessment of losses from the occupation of Ukrainian territories, which amounted to \$135 billion. The largest components of this amount are minerals (\$52.3 billion), residential real estate (\$42.8 billion) and private enterprise assets (\$18.5 billion). These three items account for 84% of the total losses [18]. A heavy blow to the functioning of the national body of Ukraine was the loss of territory and natural resources, in particular the loss of agricultural land in the Crimea and industrial capacities in Donbass, which resulted in irreparable environmental losses – contamination of drinking water sources with chemicals from destroyed enterprises. Flooding of mines carries risks of soil flooding, which can lead to the inability to live in large areas.

Control over land users’ compliance with the requirements for the protection and rational use of agricultural land in the occupied territories of Donetsk and Luhansk Regions has been lost that creates risks for the ecology of agricultural landscapes. In addition, agricultural land was negatively affected in areas where active military operations took place, and the quality of agricultural land significantly deteriorated. Many fields in Donetsk and Luhansk Regions are mined, burdened with fortifications and broken military equipment, and therefore cannot be used for sowing crops, which negatively affects farmers and the agricultural sector of the region as a whole. In the future, significant funds will need to be allocated for the reclamation of such lands in order to actively cultivate them again. Thus, according to expert estimates, it will take about 4 years and more than \$5 billion to clear all territories in Donetsk and Luhansk Regions [12]. Since the beginning of Russia’s full-scale invasion of Ukraine, at least 160 thousand units of agricultural machinery, 16 thousand units of public transport, 3.8 thousand educational institutions, 1.8 thousand cultural institutions, 580 state and local government buildings, 50 public service centers (the Administrative Services Center), 48 social centers, 31 boarding schools, 31 shopping centers and many other objects have been damaged or destroyed.

Direct financial losses of the state budget due to the loss of territories are very significant. According to a comprehensive macroeconomic assessment by the Center for Economic and Business Research (UK), the loss of tax revenues in Ukraine in 2014–2020 due to the war amounted to \$48.5 billion or UAH 1,300 billion, which in annual terms amounted to \$6.9 billion or UAH

191.0 billion [2]. Then the banking crisis of 2014 was significantly deepened by the military intervention in Donetsk and Luhansk Regions and the illegal annexation of Crimea, which significantly affected the financial and economic situation of the country as a whole, the consequences of which are felt in the operation of the system today.

The consequences of the invasion are irreparable for the industrial potential of Ukraine, in particular losses in fundamental industrial sectors: chemistry and coking chemistry, mechanical engineering, metallurgy, blocking of shipping routes and as a result – a decrease in foreign economic activity and industrial exports, destruction of production relationships with enterprises within Ukraine and in the occupied territories. And the loss of control over defense enterprises in the occupied territories and the suspension of cooperation on the supply of defense and military and dual-use products, Russian production, which were the subject of supplies under the Ukrainian-Russian interstate cooperation, caused losses to the National Military-Industrial Complex. But the most tragic consequences of the occupation of Crimea and part of Donbass were the human potential – our most valuable resource. Mass voluntary and forced relocation, emigration required victims of the conflict to adapt to new realities, where people faced problems in finding housing and work, which resulted in underutilization of intellectual and labor potential.

Mass flows of forced migration make it necessary to resettle and integrate IDPs into new communities. This problem is compounded by the lack of proper coordination between central executive authorities, central and local authorities, regional communities, and civil society organizations [7]. As a result of a full-scale Russian invasion, the Ukrainian economy will lose about \$120 billion in terms of 2026. The loss of means of production, such as equipment, machinery and production facilities, is estimated at almost one trillion US dollars. Such data comes from calculations by researchers from the Institute of World Economics in Kiel (IfW) and the University of Tübingen, published on February 14, 2024. Russia’s war against Ukraine also exerts enormous pressure on the economies of third countries that do not participate in it. Their economic losses, according to estimates of German researchers, in the period from 2022–2026 will amount to about \$260 billion. Of these, EU countries will incur losses of \$70 billion, including losses of Germany amounting to \$15–20 billion [3].

The general consequence of these losses in various sectors of the country’s life, against the background of the tragic information agenda related to Russia’s aggression, has actually paralyzed business expectations regarding Ukrainian enterprises and foreign investments, which rapidly reduces the credit rating and business attractiveness of Ukrainian businesses, and, accordingly, blocks access to new loans and affects their value. Each round of this war is a catalyst for demand for basic necessities, food, foreign currency, etc., which causes a deterioration in exchange rate dynamics and increases inflation. In general, the stratification of con-

stantly growing geopolitical threats leads to the impotence of the domestic economy and its inability to compete in the global capital market.

Therefore, domestic planning and thorough reforming of all sectors of the economy are essential in order to revive the industrial and human potential of the country, and concrete decisions taken as the basis for the revival of Ukraine in the post-war period and those that will still be initiated, methods and strategies will have value only if they are effectively implemented.

The war with Russia has been going on for two super-heavy years. During this time, the Ukrainians have managed to feel both the joy of victories and the bitterness of defeats. The consequences of Russian aggression are terrible: residential buildings, schools, hospitals, roads, railway stations and businesses have been destroyed. The energy and agricultural sectors, as well as the country's port infrastructure, have severely affected. Entire cities have been destroyed by the Russian invasion, and direct damage to the country's infrastructure reaches hundreds of billions of dollars.

As noted in the report of the analytical team of the Kyiv School of Economics (KSE), as of January 2024, the total amount of direct damage caused to Ukraine's infrastructure during the two years of war is approaching \$155 billion. This estimate also includes damage caused by the destruction of the Kakhovska Hydroelectric Power Station in June 2023. At the same time, experts note an increase in the number of damaged and destroyed infrastructure, housing stock, industry, energy, as well as education and healthcare facilities.

The greatest losses are suffered by the housing stock of Ukraine. Due to the fighting and shelling, the number of damaged and destroyed residential buildings is growing every day. As of 2024, the number of such houses exceeds 250 thousand, including 222 thousand private houses, more than 27 thousand apartment buildings and 526 dormitories. It is estimated that direct damage from the destruction of these facilities is \$58.9 billion, which is \$4.8 billion more than in 2023. The report states that most of the damage is recorded in Donetsk, Kyiv, Luhansk, Kharkiv, Chernihiv and Kherson Regions. Total infrastructure losses at the beginning of 2024 are estimated at \$36.8 billion, losses of industry and enterprises have already reached \$13.1 billion. According to the latest data, 78 small, medium and large private enterprises, as well as 348 state-owned enterprises, have been destroyed or damaged. The amount of direct damage caused by the destroyed infrastructure of the energy industry continues to grow. As of January 2024, it reaches \$9 billion, and losses in the agro-industrial complex are estimated at \$8.7 billion. In addition, at the beginning of this year, losses in housing and communal services increased significantly by \$4.5 billion and healthcare by \$1.4 billion up to \$3.1 billion [11-12].

And if we talk about the environmental losses of Ukraine during the two years of war, undoubtedly, the explosion of the Kakhovska Hydroelectric Power Station will be in the first place. The environmental disaster caused by the actions of the Russians has caused damage to Ukraine in the amount of almost \$14 billion. This is stated in the report of the Government of

Ukraine and the UN. The destruction of the Kakhovska Hydroelectric Power Station dam has caused both economic and environmental chaos in areas located downstream of the Dnieper River from the dam and station, as well as in areas upstream that have lost access to water. The consequences of the dam break are catastrophic and have affected more than 100 thousand people: 620 square kilometers of territory have been flooded in Kherson, Mykolaiv, Dnipropetrovsk and Zaporizhzhia Regions [11-12]. Many buildings, infrastructure facilities, as well as natural and cultural monuments, including historical buildings, museums and objects of religious significance, have been seriously damaged. In addition, energy and water supply, irrigation of agricultural land and the operation of river transport in the south of Ukraine have been disrupted. According to the report, direct losses caused to infrastructure and assets are estimated at \$2.79 billion, while the total amount of losses exceeds \$11 billion, the main problem is the long-term impact on the environment. The report estimates that total recovery costs will be \$5.04 billion, of which the amount of \$1.82 billion is needed in the near term.

According to the Environmental Inspectorate of the Southern District, the approximate losses of Kherson Region from a full-scale Russian invasion of Ukraine are measured in hundreds of billions of hryvnias. According to the Inspectorate's report, losses to land resources have amounted to UAH 1.7 billion, water – to UAH 2.7 million, and atmospheric air – more than UAH 144 billion. In addition, protected areas and facilities have been affected. For example, the damage caused to the Kamenska Sich Park is estimated at more than UAH 84 billion [12].

In general, according to the Minister of Environmental Protection and Natural Resources, the amount of environmental damage during the two years of war is almost \$57 billion. He has added that these are far from the final figures. Russia's aggression has caused additional greenhouse gas emissions of \$150 million tones. Every day of warfare, this figure increases. A third part of the territory of Ukraine is mined. This is not only numerical data - 174 thousand square kilometers - but also potential pollution that damages ecosystems. Since the beginning of February 2022, Russia has fired more than 100 thousand missiles and attack drones at Ukraine. Chemicals spread for thousands of kilometers are distributed not only in Ukraine, but also deposited in other countries. Military operations are currently taking place on an area of about 30 thousand square kilometers of the Ukrainian forest. Forest fires deal a double blow to the climate system, as the ability of forests to absorb carbon dioxide decreases [12].

According to Olena Shuliak, the Chairman of the State Power, Local Self-Government, Regional Development and Urban Planning, Committee, the total amount of losses from the destruction of cultural heritage monuments caused by Russian armed aggression has now exceeded \$19 billion. At the same time, as Shuliak has added, the amount of \$19 billion is only the initial one, since the destruction of historical monuments as a result of Russia's armed aggression contin-

ues. According to the report of the International Council on Monuments and Sites, during the period from February 24, 2022 to January 25, 2024, the Russian Federation destroyed or damaged 902 cultural heritage sites.

Among them, 124 facilities were of national significance, 708 were of local significance, and 70 of them have just been revealed. In particular, the destroyed facilities include 285 monuments of architecture, 269 - architecture and urban planning, 213 - history, and 33 - architecture and history. The Ministry of Culture and Information Policy has noted that as of January 25, 2024, as a result of Russia's full-scale war against Ukraine, 1,938 cultural infrastructure facilities have been damaged, not including cultural heritage sites. Of these, 314 have been destroyed, which is 16% of the total number [12].

The greatest losses of cultural infrastructure are considered to be suffered in Donetsk, Kharkiv, Kherson, Kyiv, Mykolaiv, Luhansk and Zaporizhzhia Regions and the city of Kyiv. The most affected category of cultural infrastructure facilities is club establishments, which account for 48% of the total number of destroyed or damaged facilities.

In the report of the analytical team of the Kyiv School of Economics (KSE), the most affected regions of the country are those where direct military operations were and are still carried out: Donetsk, Kharkiv, Luhansk, Mykolaiv, Zaporizhzhia, Kyiv and Chernihiv Regions. However, the true amount of damage and destruction will be estimated only after the completion of military operations on the territory of Ukraine.

Infographics

Assessment of direct losses by regions of Ukraine [12].

Donetsk
Kharkiv
Luhansk
Zaporizhzhia
Kherson
Kyiv
Mykolaiv
Chernihiv
Sumy
Dnipropetrovsk
city of Kyiv
Zhytomyr
Odesa
Poltava
Vinnytsia
Kirovohrad
Ivano-Frankivsk
Lviv
Cherkassy
Rivno
Chernivtsi
Khelnytsk
Ternopil
Volyn
Zakarpattia

Conclusion. Ukraine pays a critically high price for the unjustified geopolitical ambitions of the Russian Federation, placing on their altar the possibility of developing its economic potential, including through delays in determining its own state priorities, carrying out comprehensive reforms and creating a modern army, the establishment of constitutional norms of the rule of law and the establishment of state sovereignty.

The war has exposed all the problems of the national economy, its complete unwillingness to respond to aggression due to a lack of resources. The escalation of Russia's aggression against Ukraine has revealed the limited approach of "confrontation in exchange for the

economy", when increased economic cooperation and interdependence are considered as the main factors for preventing armed conflicts. To overcome the consequences of the war, it is essential to implement a balanced state policy of reviving the country, which would take into account the global experience of this socio-economic phenomenon.

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